

Evaluation Of Antidiabetic Potential of Acacia Nilotica Leaves Ethanolic Extract on Streptozotocin Induced Diabetic Wistar Rats

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ABSTRACT

“Diabetes mellitus”, is one of the most common non-communicable diseases worldwide. India faces several challenges in diabetes management, including a rising prevalence in urban and rural areas, lack of disease awareness among the public, limited health care facilities, high cost of treatment, suboptimal glycaemic control and rising prevalence of diabetic complications. The Ethanolic extract of Acacia Nilotica was evaluated for its Hypoglycaemic activity in normal and Streptozotocin -induced diabetic rats. The extract produced significant reduction ($p < 0.001$) in blood glucose and also had beneficial effects on the lipid profile in normal as well as streptozotocin induced diabetic rats at the end of the treatment period (21st day). The Hypoglycaemic activity of Acacia Nilotica Leaves extract was compared with Glibenclamide (0.25mg/kg b.w.) Acacia nilotica has been used in ayurvedic system of medicine for the treatment of numerous metabolic disorders from decades. The purpose of our study was to understand the molecular and biochemical mechanisms involved in protective effect of A. nilotica leaves Ethanolic extract on diabetes induced by Streptozotocin. To look for the antidiabetic effect the albino wistar rats were divided into 5 groups, each consisting of 6 animals. A single I.P. injection of streptozotocin at a dose of 40mg/kg body weight was used to cause diabetes. The rats were given the conventional medicine, Glibenclamide, at dose 0.25mg/kg body weight, respectively, until the completion of the trial. Group -1 consisted of normal rat orally administered 0.1 ml physiological saline; Group -2 consisted of streptozotocin (40mg/kg I.P.) induced diabetes rats. Group -3 consisted of streptozotocin induced diabetic rats with orally administered Glibenclamide (0.25mg/kg) once a day for 21 days. Group -4 consisted of streptozotocin induced diabetic rats with orally administered Ethanolic extract of Acacia Nilotica 50mg/kg once a day for 21 days. Group-5 consisted of streptozotocin induced diabetic rats with orally administered Ethanolic extract of Acacia Nilotica (100mg/kg) once a day for 21 days. On days 7, 14, 21, and 28, blood glucose levels were measured. **Results:** The extract's anti-diabetic properties increased when the dose was increased, and blood glucose level gradually decreased as the test drug was exposed for longer periods of time.

Keywords: Streptozotocin, Antidiabetic activity, Acacia Nilotica, Glibenclamide, Hypoglycaemic.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is heterogeneous primary disorder of carbohydrate metabolism with multiple etiological factors. It generally involves absolute or insulin resistance, or both. Whatever the cause, diabetes ultimately leads to hyperglycemia, which is the landmark of this disease syndrome and it has also been associated with an increased risk for premature arteriosclerosis due to increase in triglycerides and low-density lipoprotein levels. International diabetes Federation (IDF) estimates that more than 366 million people have diabetes worldwide and this is expected

to rise to 552 million by 2030. The number of people living with diabetes in Africa has now risen to 14.7 million. This is expected to increase to 28 million by 2030, around a 90% increase. In Kenya a recent study has shown a prevalence of 4.2% in the general population, with a prevalence of 2.2% of the rural areas and a prevalence of 12.2 % in the urban population. Diabetes mellitus is a complex progressive metabolic disease that occurs due to pancreatic beta cell dysfunction and/or insulin resistance, and manifests itself through chronically elevated glucose concentrations. Consequently, patients with diabetes require continuous monitoring

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and control of their blood glucose levels mainly through exogenous drug therapy. According to recent statistics compiled by the international Diabetes Federation (2022), 463 million adults have diabetes, which is expected to rise to 700 million by 2045, with 4.2 million deaths attributed to diabetes and its associated complications each year. It is estimated that by 2030. Diabetes has become a global economic burden, due to its ever-increasing healthcare expenditures, along with its escalating rates of mortality and morbidity and has become one of the biggest health care challenges of the 21st century. Diabetes mellitus (DM) is probably one of the oldest diseases known to man. It was first reported in Egyptian manuscript about 3000 years ago. In 1936, the distinction between type 1 and type 2 DM was clearly made. Type 2 diabetes mellitus was first described as a component of metabolic syndrome in 1988. Until recently many researchers have shown interest in the field of phytopharmacology to finding effective and safe herbal treatment for diabetes. They have carried out numerous laboratory experiments and field observations to illuminate the darkness of this field. Their findings and suggestions are reviewed here.

Acacia Nilotica is an umbrella shaped shrub and a multipurpose legume that is mainly found in Asia, Africa and Australia. Acacia Nilotica is rich in polyphenols and in ayurvedically its leaves, bark and pods are used against cancer, diabetes mellitus, inflammation, fever, menstrual, problems and diarrhea. However, the biochemical and molecule mechanisms involved in antidiabetic potential of acacia nilotica are still unknown keeping in view the high phenolic contents in acacia nilotica leaves, we hypothesized that phenols extracted from acacia nilotica might improve the glycemic status in alloxanized hyperglycemic rats. The objective of the present study was to evaluate the hypoglycemic activity of an ethanolic extract of the Acacia Nilotica Leaves in normal and streptozotocin diabetic rats.

MATERIAL AND METHODS –

- **Plant sample: -**

The leaves of Acacia Nilotica were collected from Jiwaji University, Gwalior, Madhya Pradesh. The Plant material was identified and authenticated by

botanist Dr. O.N. Maurya scientist -D & Head of office **Botanical Survey of India, Central Regional Centre, Allahabad.**

- **Preparation of the extract: –**

The leaves were washed under tap water then air dried, homogenized to fine powder and stored in airtight bottles. 10 grams of dried powder was firstly defatted with petroleum ether and then extracted with ethanol by using Soxhlet apparatus.

The solvent was evaporated to dryness and the dried crude extract was stored in air tight bottle at 4c. The ethanolic extract Acacia Nilotica was used for the whole study. (Lin et al.,1999)

- **Experimental animal:**

The study used wistar albino rats (180-220g) were used for anti-diabetic study. The mice were housed at a temperature of 25 C with 12 hours/12 hours darkness photoperiod and fed on rodent pellets and water ad libitum. The experimental protocols and procedures used in this study were approved by the Ethics Committee for the care and use of Laboratory Animals. (Abdirahman et al., J Drug Metab Toxicol 2015, 6:4 <http://dx.doi.org/10.4172/2157-7609.1000189>)

- **Induction of hyperglycemia:**

The animals were fasted overnight (14–16 hours) before induction of diabetes by STZ. The animals of group 2, 3,4 and 5 were injected 40 mg/Kg bodyweight, fresh STZ intra-peritoneal, prepared by dissolving in normal saline. On 4th post- treatment day, diabetes was confirmed by measuring fasting blood glucose levels. The rats who did not show fasting blood glucose levels >200 mg/dl, or showed any other symptomatic illness were excluded from the study. (Munazza Asad, Muhammad Aslam et al.,2011)

- **Experimental Design: -**

The experimental rat was randomly divided into five groups of six animal each.

- a) Group -1 consisted of normal rat orally administered 0.1 ml physiological saline,
- b) Group -2 consisted of streptozotocin (40mg/kg I.P.) induced diabetes rats.
- c) Group -3 consisted of streptozotocin induced diabetic rats with orally administered Glibenclamide (0.25mg/kg) once a day for 21 days.
- d) Group - 4 consisted of streptozotocin induced diabetic rats with orally administered Ethanolic extract of *Acacia Nilotica* 50mg/kg once a day for 21 days.
- e) Group-5 consisted of streptozotocin induced diabetic rats with orally administered Ethanolic extract of *Acacia Nilotica* (100mg/kg) once a day for 21 days.

- **Determination of blood glucose levels:**

Fasting blood glucose levels were determined by using the glucose oxidase method with glucometer and the blood samples were collected at an interval of day 0,3,7 after Streptozotocin induced for determining the level of glucose levels and after 7 days of Streptozotocin, extract will be given and blood samples were collected at an interval of 7, 14 and 21 days. The blood results were reported as mg/dl. (Y. Tnako, Amuhammad et al.,2013)

- **Determination of hematological parameters:**

Blood parameter and indices were determined using standard protocols (Jain NC et.al. 1986) Red blood cells count (RBC), white blood cells count (WBC). Hemoglobin (Hb), mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC), packed cell volume (PCV), mean corpuscular volume (MCV) and platelets (PLT) were determined in whole blood with EDTA anticoagulant using the Haematology analyzer. Blood Glucose levels were determined with glucometer or by glucose oxidase and glucose peroxidase method.

- **Analysis: Statistical**

Blood glucose levels were expressed in mg/ml as mean + sem. The data were statistically analyzed

using Students “t” test or Anova with multiple comparisons versus control group by Dunnett’s method values of $P < 0.05$ or less were taken as significant. (Duncan, Knapp.c et al.,1997).

CONCLUSION

Diabetes management with no side effects remains a problem for the medical system. Management of diabetes without any side effects is still a challenge to the medical system. Nevertheless, natural supplements are widely used around the world to treat diabetes, but medical research does not support their effectiveness. Therefore, the search for natural supplement from medicinal plants is being intensified probably because of its fewer side effects, readily availability and low cost. Thus, the scientific validation of medicinal plants traditionally used in the treatment and management of diabetes is necessitated. Nonetheless, natural supplements are commonly used to treat diabetes across the world, although medical evidence does not support their efficacy. As a result, the search of Natural supplementation from medicinal plants is becoming more popular, most likely as a result of its effectiveness. minimal side effects, easy accessibility, and inexpensive cost. The present study was undertaken with a view to find out whether *Acacia Nilotica* ethanolic leaves extract has hypoglycemic potential. In summary, the conventional view that *A. nilotica* plants have therapeutic capabilities in traditional medicine led to a comparative investigation of these plants' ability to prevent medication- induced diabetes.

The study examined the effects of *A. nilotica* leaf extracts on hypoglycemic activity in STZ induced Diabetic rats. The findings indicated a significant potential for the extracts, as demonstrated by a reduction in blood glucose levels when compared to the control group. The result of extracts showed significantly decreased in blood glucose levels nearby similar to standard Glibenclamide. According to the outcomes of a statistical analysis of lipid parameters, animals given extracts had the best probability of restoring their body weight, total cholesterol, total glycerides, low density lipoprotein, and high-density lipoprotein to normal.

Alkaloids and flavonoids were the main phytochemical components found in high

concentration in the ethanolic extract of acacia nilotica leaves. The ethanolic extract of the leaves contained 3.85% flavonoids and 7.2% alkaloids, according to the findings. Thus, based on comparisons to the control group, it is possible to assume that these phytochemical elements may be in charge of the antidiabetic activity, lipid profiles, and weight change assessment. However, more research is needed to determine the potential mechanism of action and to develop a comprehensive safety profile for improved therapeutic usefulness.

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